

Preserving the aesthetic of glass facades in heritage buildings with transparent aerogels

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Abstract: The history of insulating windows has evolved from two-pane windows to multi-pane glazing with reflective coatings and special gases used in between. Recent discoveries of transparent aerogels may open a new era for window and glass facade insulation, potentially leading to improved restoration practices for post-WWII cultural monuments.

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I. Introduction

The "Building Envelope Innovation Prize – Secondary Glazing Systems" challenge on HeroX¹ tasked teams with developing a system to insulate single-glazed windows, which are common in the United States, without replacing them with double- or triple-pane alternatives. It appears that only one team proposed a solution utilizing transparent aerogel. In contrast, others focused on methods involving additional glass panes or the application of heat-reflective coatings to existing windows.²

This essay describes the path to transparent window aerogel insulators and discusses their potential use in post-WWII building restoration.

II. Window insulation development

The concept of using an air gap between two windows in a series is not new; however, in recent decades, the thickness of this air gap has steadily increased, leading to the development of double- and multi-pane windows. These systems consist of panes of glass set within a single frame, with a thin layer of air or a specialized gas between each pane. However, there is a practical limit to this approach. When the air gap is less than 10 mm, convection within the gap can undermine its insulating properties. To overcome this limitation, inert gases such as argon and krypton, which exhibit lower thermal conductivity, are employed in place of air.

The ongoing challenge lies in further enhancing the efficiency of window insulation without resorting to multi-pane systems, which may not always offer a cost-effective solution. Instead, developing efficient and affordable methods for improving window and façade insulation is essential. Of course, in cases where window frames are poorly insulated or have structural defects, replacing the windows may be the most practical solution, as inadequate framing can negate the benefits of advanced glazing. However, in situations where the framing is intact and well-insulated, an alternative solution could involve applying a transparent, perforated layer to the surface of the glass.

III. Way to aerogel insulation

Using small air gaps as an effective insulator has been understood for centuries, practically and theoretically. Small air pockets insulate much better than a layer of air. Historically, the challenge has been the lack of transparent materials suitable for use in windows. The issue was the refractive index of the air pockets within the material.

Recently, a study on producing transparent silica aerogel derived from wood pulp has gained attention.³ This research aims to reduce the production costs of aerogels, which have traditionally been expensive. Initiatives such as those on HeroX facilitate advances in scientific research. The

1 ["Building Envelope Innovation Prize - Secondary Glazing Systems | HeroX"](#). *www.herox.com*. Retrieved 2025-04-15.

2 ["Building Envelope Innovation Prize - Secondary Glazing Systems | HeroX"](#). *www.herox.com*. Retrieved 2025-04-15.

3 Åkerfelt, Mia; Wilczyńska, Anna; Fainholtz, Tzafir (2023). "From crisis housing to cultural heritage. The changing views on exported Finnish wooden houses from the post-war decades". *Cities in evolution*. Istanbul: DRUM Press: 121–130.

SiCellA product, researched by Eldho Abraham et al., is notable for its ability to adhere to glass or plastic surfaces through electrostatic charge, eliminating the need for adhesive bonding. This approach reduces the need to fabricate composites specifically for this purpose.

In some applications, composite transparent aerogels could prove helpful, especially if a heat-reflective layer couldn't be attached to the aerogel itself or given other purposes. A multilayer sandwich consisting of aerogel and foil would provide such features. However, further research is required to ensure that these materials are compatible with each other, that light transmission remains optimal, and that the thermal insulation properties of the aerogel are not compromised.

IV. Glass walls insulation

High-efficiency aerogel insulation, could be applied in the restoration of modern cultural monuments, particularly those with glass facades or outdated insulation materials in their walls.

In house restoration, the goal is always to preserve as many original components as possible. However, replacing windows with double or triple-glazed units has often been the solution when no other technology is available. While this approach is practical, it does not always match the original design perfectly. In such instances, using transparent aerogels or transparent aerogel composites could resolve these discrepancies. For example, the recent restoration of the Bratislava-Vinohrady train station building (Slovakia, not a cultural monument) involved replacing the original glass walls with network of metal frames. The restored structure looks different as a result (Figures 1 and 2). Using transparent aerogels could have preserved the original aesthetic while improving the building's energy efficiency.

Figure 1. Bratislava-Vinohrady before restoration

Figure 2. Bratislava-Vinohrady after restoration

Author of the photograph: Matej Grochal

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A similar situation could arise at the Duchcov train station building (Czech Republic), a cultural monument awaiting restoration (Figure 3), where maintaining the original appearance is crucial.

Figure 3. Duchcov train station in 2024